

BIOTRAILS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. INTEGRATED LCA AND EEMRIO METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH	4
2.1. Analytical Framework and Methodological Evolution.....	4
2.2. Data Sources and Databases.....	5
2.3. Detailed Methods Implementation	6
3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS	8
REFERENCES	11

Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
PSDM	Participatory System Dynamic Modelling
BCS	Biodiversity-Climate-Society Nexus
BIM	Biodiversity Impact Metric
kgCO ₂ eq	Kilogram carbon dioxide equivalents
EEMRIO	Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output
GHG	Greenhouse gases
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LUC	Land use change
MRIOA	Multi-Regional Input-Output Analysis
PDF	Potential disappeared fraction
REX	Resolved EXIOBASE

ABSTRACT

This report synthesizes the methodologies and findings from Deliverables 3.5 and 3.6 of the BIOTRAILS project, detailing an integrated analytical framework using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) analysis as a means of identifying leverage points for reducing environmental impacts along the value chain. The primary objective was to evaluate the environmental impacts, with a specific focus on biodiversity loss and climate change, across four key value chains: cocoa production in Peru, fishery and aquaculture in Greece, gold mining in Ghana, and handicrafts in Brazil [1]. The methodology section, as the core of this publication, explains the transition from high-level, aggregated EEMRIO analysis and spatially resolved EEMRIO data (REX) to more detailed, scenario-based LCA, which is essential for identifying actionable levers for transformative change [2]. Key findings across the case studies reveal significant insights into impact hotspots, the outsourcing of environmental burdens to different countries, and the nuanced trade-offs and synergies between economic activity and environmental outcomes [2],[3].

1. INTRODUCTION

The Biodiversity-Climate-Society (BCS) Nexus illustrates the relationship between the three factors, with changes in one asset influencing the others in both positive and negative connections. This makes policy difficult to operationalize due to the often conflicting end results. This publication addresses these challenges by presenting a detailed methodological framework for a quantitative, data-driven analysis of the BCS Nexus. It documents the evolution and application of an integrated approach using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output (EEMRIO) databases [2],[3]. This framework is designed to move beyond a purely qualitative understanding of system interdependencies to provide a robust, evidence-based foundation for identifying and simulating potential interventions for biodiversity-relevant transformative change [2],[3]. This work is explicitly positioned to inform and enhance the broader Participatory System Dynamic Model (PDSM) and policy co-design efforts of the BIOTRAILS project [1]. The goal of this technical publication is to present the methodologies, data sources, and analytical frameworks of this integrated approach, as outlined in deliverables D3.5 and D3.6, with a focus on their application across four key value chains: cocoa production in Peru, fishery and aquaculture in Greece, gold mining in Ghana, and handicrafts in Brazil.

2. INTEGRATED LCA AND EEMRIO METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This section outlines the detailed methodology for assessing the environmental impacts of the four BIOTRAILS case studies, synthesizing the approaches from Deliverables D3.5 and D3.6. The approach is centered on integrating EEMRIO and LCA to achieve a comprehensive, multi-scale understanding of value chain impacts. The approach demonstrates a clear methodological progression, starting with a broad overview and moving towards granular, actionable analysis.

2.1. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGICAL EVOLUTION

The BIOTRAILS analytical framework is built on the synergy of two powerful yet distinct tools: LCA and EEMRIO analysis. EEMRIO databases, such as FABIO and EXIOBASE, provide a comprehensive, high-level overview of economic interdependencies and supply chain linkages across multiple regions and sectors [4]. This approach is particularly effective for quantifying the environmental

footprint of an entire sector, revealing how impacts are "outsourced" from consumption regions to production regions through global trade [4]. For example, it can determine that the climate change impact of fish from Greece is not only felt in Greece but also in countries that supply feed ingredients or energy to the Greek aquaculture sector. This macro-economic perspective is invaluable for identifying large-scale environmental hotspots and informing global policy.

Conversely, LCA offers a more detailed, process-level analysis, quantifying the specific environmental impacts associated with each stage of a product's life cycle [5]. This includes everything from the extraction of raw materials and production to distribution, use, and disposal. This level of detail is crucial for identifying operational-level levers for transformative change. For instance, an LCA can determine that a farmer's choice to use organic instead of inorganic fertilizer has a measurable impact on greenhouse gas emissions, a change that would be obscured in an aggregated EEMRIO model.

The framework is not static; it demonstrates a clear methodological evolution across the deliverables. The initial work in D3.5 used a broader EEMRIO analysis to map supply chains and identify hotspots [2]. The subsequent work in D3.6 deepened this analysis by using a more resolved EEMRIO database (Resolved EXIOBASE, or REX) for the gold and handicrafts sectors, separating previously aggregated sectors (fishery and aquaculture), and developing detailed LCAs. This progression from a broad "what" (where are the hotspots?) to a specific "how" (how can we change operations to reduce impacts?) is central to the project's analytical rigor. This detailed assessment of both inputs and impacts associated with each of the distinct projects was able to inform the quantitative aspect of the PSDM model.

2.2. DATA SOURCES AND DATABASES

A range of state-of-the-art databases and tools were employed to support the analysis:

- Multi-Regional Input-Output (MRIO) Databases:
 - FABIO (Food and Agriculture Biomass Input-Output): Used for the cocoa case study, providing detailed information on the agricultural sector and its global interconnections. It includes environmental data on land and water use, GHG emissions, land use change (LUC), and fertilizer application [4].
 - EXIOBASE: Employed for the gold, and fishery and aquaculture case studies, covering a wide range of economic sectors and regions with integrated environmental data. It was used to analyze the interconnectedness of these sectors within their economies and trace supply chains [6].
 - Resolved EXIOBASE (REX): An improved, highly resolved version of EXIOBASE used in the later gold and handicrafts analyses. This database provides more detailed, direct biodiversity loss impacts than the more aggregated versions [7].
- Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Databases:
 - ecoinvent: A comprehensive database containing data for thousands of processes and environmental flows. It was the primary source for populating the LCIs for the cocoa, gold, and fishery/aquaculture case studies, enabling a detailed assessment of foreground processes at the unit process level [8].
- Other Key Data Sources:
 - Spatially-explicit data: The CROPGRIDS dataset provided global spatial distribution for cocoa. The Maus et al. dataset [9] was used for mining areas. IUCN Red List and Birdlife Data Zone provided species-specific data, enabling highly resolved spatial analysis [10].
 - FAOSTAT & Sea Around Us: These databases provided country- and species-specific production, trade, and export data, which was crucial for contextualizing the EEMRIO

- and LCA findings [11], [12].
- Published Literature: A variety of published LCA studies and technical papers were used to inform and validate the LCIs and scenario assumptions where specific data was not available from the primary databases.
- Analytical Tools:
 - Activity Browser and Brightway: Open-source software packages for LCA modeling and analysis that provided a user-friendly interface for database management and result analysis [13], [14].
 - R and Python Scripts: Custom scripts were developed for data processing, aggregation, and visualization of supply chains and environmental footprints.

2.3. DETAILED METHODS IMPLEMENTATION

The methodological implementation was a multi-step process, with different approaches tailored to each case study and impact category. The detailed methods below illustrate the application of the analytical framework described previously.

a. Supply Chain Tracing and Hotspot Identification

The value chains for cocoa, gold, and aquaculture/fisheries were traced using multi-regional input-output databases [2]. This involved identifying the relevant sectors and regions and analyzing the economic and physical flows between them. This tracing allowed for the quantification of economic contributions and dependencies throughout the supply chains. The analysis mathematically represents the economy using a Leontief inverse matrix, which describes the direct and indirect inputs required by each sector to produce its output. This matrix is used to calculate the total requirements vector for a given sector, capturing the ripple effects of demand changes that propagate through the entire economy. In the context of the BIOTRAILS case studies, this method quantifies the direct and indirect inputs for each industry, revealing which sectors are major suppliers of inputs. It is also used to trace downstream supply chains, identifying the consumers of the final products, thus enabling the attribution of environmental impacts to consumption patterns.

b. Environmental Assessment

The environmental assessment encompassed a wide range of stressors, including GHG emissions, land and water use, fertilizer application, and various pollutants like NO_x, SO_x, PM, and heavy metals [3]. The framework transitioned from a highly aggregated, economic-based assessment in Deliverable D3.5, which used EEMRIO databases to derive emissions factors and resource use based on economic activity, to a detailed, process-based LCA in Deliverable D3.6. A baseline Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) was developed for each value chain, which was then used to calculate environmental impacts using established methodologies [3]. The ReCiPe 2016 v1.03 (H) methodology [15] was used to calculate biodiversity loss, measured in species.year, which represents the number of species expected to disappear over a year due to the assessed activities. For climate change, the IPCC 2021 methodology was applied, with climate change impacts measured in kgCO₂eq [16].

c. Biodiversity Loss Assessment by Case Study

Cocoa Production in Peru

Biodiversity loss due to land use for cocoa cultivation in Peru was analyzed using two complementary methodologies [3]. The **UNEP-SETAC recommended approach (Method 1)** was used to compare biodiversity impacts at a macroscopic, ecoregion level across global cocoa producers. This method allowed for a broad comparison of Peru's impacts relative to other countries, revealing that Peru has a lower-than-average impact per tonne of cocoa produced [3]. This is largely due to high cocoa yields, which effectively offset the impacts of increased production

on biodiversity [3]. However, this high-level view can be misleading.

To address this, a more highly resolved approach, the **Biodiversity Impact Metric (BIM) approach (Method 2)**, was implemented [3]. This method dives into high spatial detail at the grid cell scale, combining local biodiversity intactness (Mean Species Abundance - MSA) with global biodiversity importance (Range Rarity - RR). This analysis revealed a significant finding: while Peru's overall impact may be low, the impacts are highly concentrated in specific areas of high biodiversity importance, such as the central forest region. The province of San Martin has the highest total biodiversity loss impact due to its production amounts, but the province of Amazonas has the highest impact per hectare. This multi-scale analysis demonstrates that the problem is not just about the total magnitude of impact, but about where that impact is located. A seemingly low average impact can conceal a highly concentrated, severe local problem, requiring a nuanced, spatially-explicit policy response rather than a general one.

The LCA for cocoa production further quantified biodiversity impacts from other factors, such as pollution and resource use, using the ReCiPe method [15]. This analysis showed that cultivation impacts overwhelmingly outweigh those of processing, packaging, distribution, and end-of-life, accounting for 98% of the total impact. Scenario assessments for cultivation revealed that the largest potential reductions in biodiversity impacts come from replacing inorganic fertilizers with organic ones and eliminating pesticide use.

Gold Mined in Ghana

The biodiversity impacts of gold mining were assessed using two methods, building on the initial EEMRIO analysis. The first, based on the **UNEP-SETAC and REX databases**, identified biodiversity loss hotspots at the ecoregion level. This analysis revealed that Ghana is a global biodiversity hotspot for mining, accounting for a disproportionately high 1.86% of global land-use-related biodiversity loss for all mined materials, while using only 1.06% of its land for mining [3]. This finding shifts the focus from the quantity of land used to the ecological value of that land.

A second, more spatially-explicit method using **Grid Cell Resolution Spatially-Explicit Species Loss Factors** corroborated this finding. It used updated mining maps and combined local biodiversity intactness (MSA) with global biodiversity importance (RR) to quantify Endemic Species Abundance (ESA) loss [3]. This method confirmed that Ghana's gold mines are located in areas with high biodiversity importance, with a total ESA loss of 0.034% of assessed plant and animal species [3]. The implications of this are significant: Ghana's high biodiversity impact is due to the strategic location of mines in ecologically sensitive regions, not simply the total area of land disturbed.

The LCA for gold mining, which included mining, refining, and distribution, confirmed that the mining and refining stages are responsible for the vast majority of environmental impacts [3]. It found that the primary contributors to ecosystem quality damage are freshwater ecotoxicity and eutrophication, followed by climate change impacts on terrestrial systems. This suggests that land use, as quantified by ReCiPe, is not the only major driver of biodiversity loss in mining activities; pollution is also a critical factor [3]. The analysis highlights that reducing pollution from Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) and tailings storage facilities (TSFs) and managing mercury use in artisanal mining are critical for mitigating biodiversity loss [3].

Fishery and Aquaculture in Greece

The initial EEMRIO analysis revealed that a significant portion of environmental impacts from Greek fisheries and aquaculture is outsourced [2].

For this case study, the LCA methodology separated fishery and aquaculture due to their distinct

value chains and inputs [3]. The LCA for aquaculture identified that feed production is, by far, the largest contributor to both biodiversity loss and climate change impacts. It accounts for the majority of the total impact, with other stages like hatchery, farming, and processing having a much smaller contribution. This finding highlights a critical causal chain: a seemingly sustainable choice (farmed fish) can have a significant environmental footprint in a distant, unrelated ecosystem (deforestation for feed crops). A key implication is that for effective change, local practices must be combined with international supply chain optimization, particularly by sourcing feed from low-impact regions and investigating alternative feed sources.

For fisheries, a species-specific biodiversity loss assessment was developed to address a gap in standard LCA methods, which do not adequately capture the impacts of overfishing [17]. This analysis used a global Characterisation Factor (CF) for overexploitation, measured in Potential Disappeared Fraction (PDF), to evaluate species-specific impacts [17]. The results indicated that the type of fish caught is a critical determinant of biodiversity loss, with species like greater amberjack having a much higher impact per tonne than species like squid or octopus [17]. The LCA also found that the fishing method itself is a significant variable, with trawlers and long-line fishing having different impact profiles. This suggests that shifting consumer preferences and optimizing fishing methods are crucial levers for change.

Handicrafts in Brazil

This case study is unique, as the analysis aimed to quantify the avoided environmental impacts of the handicraft sector, rather than its direct impacts [3]. The methodology used the EXIOBASE database to calculate the environmental stressors (land use, GHG, pollutants) associated with the economic revenue generated by other sectors that would otherwise compete for the land used by indigenous communities. The premise is that the economic activity of producing handicrafts supports indigenous communities and protects their lands. These lands, when legally designated as Indigenous Lands (ILs), have been shown to have significantly lower deforestation rates compared to unprotected areas.

This method demonstrates that economic activity can be a tool for conservation. By supporting the handicrafts sector, policymakers are not just creating jobs; they are actively preventing environmental damage from higher-impact sectors like cattle ranching, logging, and mining from expanding into biodiverse areas. The value of the handicrafts sector is therefore not just in its economic output but in the environmental "return on investment" of protecting indigenous lands.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The methodological framework presented in this publication, integrating LCA and EEMRIO analysis, provides a powerful and nuanced tool for understanding and managing the complex interdependencies of the BCS Nexus. The work across the four BIOTRAILS case studies has demonstrated a progression from broad, aggregated impact identification to detailed, process-specific analysis and scenario-based intervention planning.

Main Strengths of the Integrated Framework

- The primary strength of the integrated LCA/EEMRIO approach is its ability to provide a holistic, multi-scale view of Nexus challenges. EEMRIO analysis offers a macro-level perspective, mapping global supply chain dependencies and the outsourcing of environmental burdens to different countries [2]. This is crucial for understanding the international dimensions of local problems. Conversely, LCA provides a micro-level, operational view, identifying specific points in the value chain where production decisions can directly alter environmental outcomes [3]. This combination allows for the identification

of both macro-economic and local-level interventions, ensuring that solutions are targeted and comprehensive.

- Furthermore, the framework supports the development of context-specific solutions. The case studies have repeatedly shown that a "one-size-fits-all" approach is ineffective. The analyses, through their detailed spatial and process-level resolutions, provide a scientific foundation for tailoring policy recommendations. For example, the critical levers for reducing biodiversity loss in cocoa are different from those for gold mining, despite both involving land-use change [3]. In cocoa, the focus is on sustainable intensification and agroforestry, whereas in gold mining, it is on strategic mine location and pollution control [3]. This contextual specificity enhances the framework's practical utility for achieving transformative change.
- Finally, the methodology is dynamic and forward-looking. By using scenario analysis, it can move beyond a static snapshot of current impacts. It can simulate prospective interventions and evaluate their effectiveness over time, revealing "windows of opportunity" for policy action. This is a crucial step in moving from merely describing the problem to actively supporting the design of effective, future-oriented solutions.

Limitations and Future Work

- Despite its strengths, the integrated framework still faces limitations, primarily related to data resolution and availability. While Deliverable D3.6 made significant improvements, standard LCA methodologies still lack robust means of quantifying certain marine biodiversity impacts, such as those from sea-bed damage, fish disease, or invasive species [17]. This can skew results, as seen in the aquaculture case study, where the calculated impacts were dominated by land-based feed production, while concurrently potentially underestimating marine-based damage [17]. For the gold and handicrafts sectors, the EEMRIO data, even in its resolved form, is still aggregated, making it difficult to fully represent the complexities of informal or artisanal value chains.

The following table summarizes the key findings and transformative potential for each case study, providing a synthesis of the EEMRIO and LCA results.

Table 1. Summary of EEMRIO and LCA Findings and Transformative Potential

Case Study	Key EEMRIO Finding	Key LCA Finding	Key Transformative Potential
Cocoa (Peru)	Biodiversity impact from exports grew 20-fold from 2000-2020, with the EU and US as major drivers.	Cultivation is the major GHG and biodiversity hotspot. Monoculture has higher yields but lower overall biodiversity benefits than agroforestry.	Sustainable intensification on existing farms, adoption of agroforestry, replacement of inorganic fertilizers with organic, and optimization of processing energy sources.
Fishery & Aquaculture (Greece)	The majority of environmental impacts are outsourced to countries supplying feed and energy.	The greatest impact is from feed production. For fisheries, the fishing method (trawling vs. long-line) and species targeted are critical determinants of impact.	Sourcing feed ingredients from low-impact regions, reducing energy use with on-site renewables, shifting consumer preferences to lower-impact fish, and optimizing fishing methods.
Gold (Ghana)	Ghana's gold mining is a global biodiversity hotspot, accounting for a	The main GHG driver is the electricity source used in mining	Strategic mine location to avoid high-biodiversity areas, substitution of fossil

	disproportionately high 1.86% of global mining biodiversity loss.	operations, not the physical mining process itself.	fuels with on-site renewables, and enhanced TSF management to prevent pollution.
Handicrafts (Brazil)	The sector creates "avoided impacts" by preventing other higher-impact sectors (e.g., cattle ranching, logging) from expanding into Indigenous Lands.	A full LCA was not performed due to data limitations, but the data indicates the environmental benefits of protecting indigenous lands from competing sectors.	Policy support for indigenous land rights and cultural products to actively promote conservation by creating a "buffer" against deforestation pressure.

REFERENCES

- [1] “BIOTRAILS Nexus framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change,” Chair of Ecological Systems Design. Accessed: Jan. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://esd.ifu.ethz.ch/research/research-projects/research-and-theses/biotrails.html>
- [2] “https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/BIOTRAILS_D3.5_Updated-LCA-and-EEMRIO-data-A.pdf.” Accessed: Oct. 06, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/BIOTRAILS_D3.5_Updated-LCA-and-EEMRIO-data-A.pdf
- [3] “https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/241209_BIOTRAILS_D3.6_Updated-LCA-and-EEMRIO.pdf.” Accessed: Oct. 06, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/241209_BIOTRAILS_D3.6_Updated-LCA-and-EEMRIO.pdf
- [4] M. Bruckner *et al.*, “FABIO—The Construction of the Food and Agriculture Biomass Input-Output Model,” *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 53, no. 19, pp. 11302–11312, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1021/acs.est.9b03554.
- [5] S. Hellweg, E. Benetto, M. A. J. Huijbregts, F. Verones, and R. Wood, “Life-cycle assessment to guide solutions for the triple planetary crisis,” *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.*, vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 471–486, July 2023, doi: 10.1038/s43017-023-00449-2.
- [6] K. Stadler *et al.*, “EXIOBASE 3: Developing a Time Series of Detailed Environmentally Extended Multi-Regional Input-Output Tables,” *J. Ind. Ecol.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 502–515, 2018, doi: 10.1111/jiec.12715.
- [7] L. Cabernard, S. Pfister, and S. Hellweg, “Resolved Exiobase version 3 (REX3).” Zenodo, Apr. 01, 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10354283.
- [8] “ecoinvent - Data with purpose.” ecoinvent. Accessed: Sept. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ecoinvent.org/>
- [9] V. Maus *et al.*, “A global-scale data set of mining areas,” *Sci. Data*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 289, Sept. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41597-020-00624-w.
- [10] “The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species,” IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Accessed: Sept. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/en>
- [11] “Statistics | FAO | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.” Accessed: Sept. 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fao.org/statistics/en>
- [12] “Sea Around Us | Fisheries, Ecosystems and Biodiversity.” Accessed: Oct. 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.seaaroundus.org/data/#/eez>
- [13] B. Steubing, D. de Koning, A. Haas, and C. L. Mutel, “The Activity Browser — An open source LCA software building on top of the brightway framework,” *Softw. Impacts*, vol. 3, p. 100012, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.simpa.2019.100012.
- [14] C. Mutel, “Brightway: An open source framework for Life Cycle Assessment,” *J. Open Source Softw.*, vol. 2, no. 12, p. 236, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.21105/joss.00236.
- [15] M. A. J. Huijbregts *et al.*, “ReCiPe2016: a harmonised life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level,” *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 138–147, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y.
- [16] Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), *Climate Change 2021 – The Physical Science Basis: Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023. doi: 10.1017/9781009157896.
- [17] C. Stanford-Clark, E. Loiseau, and A. Helias, “Fisheries Impact Pathway: Making Global and Regionalised Impacts on Marine Ecosystem Quality Accessible in Life Cycle Impact Assessment,” *Sustainability*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. 3870, May 2024, doi: 10.3390/su16093870.